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Peat Depth Distribution Across Northern Peatland Regions as Influenced by Different Environmental Factors

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Key Points:

- Peat depth across northern peatlands is highly variable and can not be explained by individual environmental controls
- Models combining multiple variables can predict peat depth with moderate accuracy, with a machine learning model working best
- The environmental controls of peatland extent differ from controls on peat depth and ca. 50-100 Pg peat carbon is stored below 3 m depth

35 **Abstract**

36 Peatlands are critical to global biogeochemical cycles because their large accumulations of
37 organic carbon (OC) and nitrogen (N). Broadscale peatland depth maps are needed to assess
38 stocks of OC and N. We used a large peat-core dataset ($n=7,111$) to assess which environmental
39 variables control peat depth across the extratropical northern hemisphere, testing climatic
40 variables, topography, mineral soil texture and peatland extent. We find that no single
41 environmental variable can accurately predict peat depth. Rather, analyses with multiple
42 regression models show that greater peat depth is linked to a combination of low potential
43 evapotranspiration, warm summers, and limited intra-annual climatic seasonality. At broad
44 scales, the environmental controls of peatland extent are different from controls on peatland
45 depth. This supports the use of methods that treat peatland extent separately from depth
46 when quantifying peat OC stocks. We evaluate different upscaling methods for peat depth
47 mapping and find that random forest machine learning works better than geographically
48 weighted regression or thematic upscaling because the random forest method is more robust
49 with clustered and spatially variable peat depth data. Consistent with earlier studies, we
50 estimate total northern peat stocks of 400 ± 150 Pg OC and 10 ± 7 Pg N. A large part of this peat,
51 containing ca. 50-100 Pg OC, is stored below the 0-3 m depth interval used for global soil OC
52 inventories. Future peatland mapping efforts should target high-resolution maps of individual
53 peatland basins. Such maps will enable more focused studies into the processes that constrain
54 vertical peat accumulation across space and time.

55 **1. Introduction**

56 Peatlands are primarily found in Boreal and Arctic biomes, but also in the humid Tropics
57 (Joosten & Clarke, 2002; Kivinen & Pakarinen, 1981). As a consistent sink of atmospheric carbon
58 (C), peatlands have been an important component in the global carbon cycle throughout the
59 Holocene (Brovkin et al., 2016; MacDonald et al., 2006; Yu et al., 2014). Peatland ecosystems
60 are also important in the global nitrogen (N) cycle, storing large amounts of N and as sources or
61 sinks of the greenhouse gas nitrous oxide (Hugelius et al., 2020). However, there is a lack of
62 consistency in estimates of peatland extent, peatland depth, and stocks of organic carbon (OC)
63 and total nitrogen (TN) in peatlands (Hugelius et al., 2020; Julie Loisel et al., 2017; Nichols &
64 Peteet, 2021; Yu et al., 2014). Studies in recent decades have quantified northern peat C stocks
65 ranging from 270 to >1000 Pg OC, but estimates of ca 400-500 Pg OC are most frequently used
66 (Yu et al., 2021). These broad-scale estimates of peat OC stocks have often made by combining
67 estimated peatland extent with estimated local peat OC density (e.g., as kg peat OC per m^2).
68 Peatland extent remains poorly mapped, but significant improvements are being made with
69 application of new digital soil mapping techniques (Minasny et al., 2019), including machine-
70 learning algorithms (Melton et al., 2022). Less progress has been made regarding estimates of
71 peat depth, and improved peat depth maps are needed for estimates of peatland C and N
72 density and to support the development or validation of peatland models (Hugelius et al.,
73 2020).
74 Peat formation occurs when decomposition rates are lower than plant litter formation, a
75 condition which is promoted under waterlogged, anoxic conditions. Because peat formation
76 largely depends on soil saturation, local scale controls on soil water retention such as

77 topography and substrate permeability are important. Peat depth also differs locally depending
78 on location within a peatland complex (Pluchon et al., 2014). Because of this the physiography
79 of the landscape as well as peatland morphology has an overarching control on peat depth at
80 local and landscape scale (Ehnavall et al., 2024; Loisel et al., 2017). At broader scales, across
81 regions and continents, peatland depth and morphology have been linked to climatic controls
82 such as air temperature, precipitation patterns, and potential evapotranspiration (PET)
83 (Charman et al., 2015; Gallego-Sala et al., 2018; Kivinen & Pakarinen, 1981; Masing et al., 2010;
84 Tanneberger et al., 2021). Incoming growing season Photosynthetically Active Radiation (PAR)
85 has also been shown to affect plant production and peat formation rates (Loisel et al., 2012). It
86 is likely that peatland depth is linked to all of these environmental factors, but that there are
87 large variations depending on the scale and location. Improved modeling and mapping of
88 peatland dynamics requires deeper understanding of the processes, and associated
89 environmental variables, that control vertical peat accumulation.
90 To move from individual measurements of peat depth to full spatial coverage in peat depth
91 maps, different approaches for upscaling can be used. Older maps have applied thematic
92 upscaling, by calculated average peat depths for different thematic peatland classes or regions
93 or classes of wetlands (Köchy et al., 2015). More robust spatial estimates of soil properties can
94 be reached using digital soil mapping techniques (Mishra et al., 2013). Such methods may build
95 on geostatistical interpolation based on spatial autocorrelation between dependent data and
96 spatially varying environmental variables, for example in Geographically Weighted Regression
97 (GWR) (Brunsdon et al., 1996). Because peatland and permafrost landforms exhibit very large
98 spatial variability (e.g. between micro-topography forms) and non-linearity, they are difficult to
99 map with digital soil mapping techniques that rely on spatial autocorrelation (de Brogniez et al.,
100 2015; Siewert et al., 2021). There is an increased use of machine learning algorithms, such as
101 random forest and support vector machines, which do not rely on spatial autocorrelation
102 between data points (Wadoux et al., 2020).
103 Information on northern peatland depth is needed for spatial upscaling and modeling of
104 biogeochemical processes associated to peatlands. Despite this, there is no systematic analysis
105 in the literature of which environmental factors primarily control broad-scale peat depth
106 patterns in northern peatlands. In this study we explore spatial patterns and environmental
107 controls of peatland depth across the extratropical northern hemisphere ($>23^{\circ}$ N) and evaluate
108 how the use of different peat mapping techniques affects estimates of peat C and N stocks. We
109 analyze how climate, topography, and edaphic factors co-vary with observed peat depth
110 ($n=7,111$ peat cores), including analyses at different scales of spatial data aggregation. We
111 further explore how the use of different techniques for peat depth mapping (thematic
112 upscaling, geographically weighted regression and random forest machine learning) affect
113 estimates of peat OC and TN stocks.

114 2 Methods

115 The methods applied in this paper follow two main themes in patterns and upscaling of peat
116 depth across the northern extra-tropical terrestrial land surface (defined as north of 23°
117 latitude, includes 67 M km² of land area). Section 2.1 describes analyses of observational peat
118 core data to assess general patterns in peat depth data and environmental controls of peat
119 depth across the region. Sections 2.2 and 2.3 describe different approaches to map and upscale

120 peat depth and peat OC/TN stocks across the region. All spatial analyses were performed in the
121 software ArcGIS 10 (ESRI, Redlands, CA, USA). Statistical analyses were performed in PAST 3.1
122 (Hammer et al., 2001), R (R Core Team, 2020) or ArcGIS 10. Mean values are reported with ± 1
123 SD. Statistical tests are two-sided and considered significant if $p < 0.05$.

124 2.1 Analyses of peat core data

125 The peat core data analyzed in this paper is identical to the dataset presented and used in
126 Hugelius et al., (2020), but analyzed in different ways and with different results. For details on
127 data sources and compilation we refer to the original publication. In total, 7111 geolocated
128 peat cores with data on full peat depth were compiled. For 782 sites there was data on peat
129 depth, peat OC content (weight % OC) and dry bulk density. For 105 sites there was additional
130 data on peat TN content (weight % TN).

131 2.1.1 Analyses and spatial clustering of point observations

132 To more accurately model the relationships between peat depth patterns and environmental
133 factors at regional to continental scales, we wanted to identify those regions where there are
134 sufficient peat depth observations to make robust local scale estimates of mean peat depths.
135 These analyses were done using the neighborhood statistics, point density and point statistics
136 toolsets in ArcMap 10.3.1. We isolated regions where the data density exceeded a range of
137 thresholds of point observations density per square kilometer. The chosen thresholds were
138 equivalent to $\geq 4, 6, 8, 10, 15, 20$ and 30 replicate peat depth observations within a 30 km radius
139 circle (which has an area of $2,800$ km²). These thresholds were chosen based on visual
140 inspection of plotted data density. Within these same circular neighborhoods, we calculated
141 the mean, SD and range of observed peat depths. The aggregated properties of these different
142 neighborhoods were then extracted to new point data and used as input in multiple linear
143 regression and Geographically Weighted Regression (GWR) models. We thus ended up with a
144 range of spatially aggregated data going from limited to high point density. In addition to the
145 effect of point density, we explored the effect of spatial resolution in the environmental
146 explanatory data by applying a smoothing kernel of 90×90 km on the environmental proxy data.

147 2.1.2 Exploratory multiple linear regression

148 All regression analyses were performed on log-transformed peat depth data ($n = 7,011$; sites
149 with data gaps for environmental variables were omitted). We performed exploratory
150 regression analyses to identify environmental variables that exhibited significant linear
151 relationships to peat depth across the full extent of data. The environmental variables were
152 selected based on literature studies and included factors known to influence peatland extent,
153 depth and morphology. They included incoming solar radiation, temperature, precipitation,
154 topography, mineral soil texture and peatland extent. Table 1 describes the selected variables
155 and our hypotheses of how they could influence peatland depth (for more extended
156 explanations and references see Table S1). Exploratory multiple regression analyses (using
157 ArcGIS 10.3) were run for all peat sites as well as for the full range of the spatially aggregated
158 data points. For each level of site aggregation, we identified the strongest model (highest
159 adjusted R^2) which fulfilled the following criteria: (1) coefficient p -value < 0.05 , (2) a Variance
160 Inflation Factor < 7.5 , and (3) did not contain unexpected variable combinations. The latter

161 occurred if a model included combinations of variables which were considered redundant (e.g.
 162 only climate seasonality) or which showed a response directly opposite to what is expected
 163 based on the literature (see Table 1 for explanations). If several models had the same Adjusted
 164 R^2 , we chose the model with the lowest score for Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC). Note that
 165 most models had non-normally distributed p-values and spatially autocorrelated residuals. This
 166 indicates that our model lacks important local to regional scale variables. In the GWR runs
 167 (section 2.3.3), this problem manifested as very high condition values (>30, indicating an
 168 unstable model) which tended to cluster in regions characterized by a high point data density
 169 and large local variability in peat depth (e.g. southern Finland).

170
 171 Table 1. Summary of the environmental variables analyzed in relation to peatland depth in the individual
 172 peat cores as well as to the final maps of peat depth, peat extent and scaled peat OC stocks. Note that
 173 the variables are purposefully identical to the input data used by Hugelius et al. (2020) to map peat
 174 depth.

Variable group	Description	Hypothesis
Radiation	PAR: Photosynthetically Active Radiation summed during the growing season (April to October; period 1961-1990).	+ High PAR increases plant productivity in peatlands.
Temperature	MAAT: Mean Annual Air temperature (period 1950-2000)	+ High MAAT increases plant productivity in peatlands (- but may also increase peat decomposition rates and reduce permafrost protection of peat).
	MTWQ: Mean Temperature of the years Warmest Quarter (period 1950-2000)	+ High MTWQ increases plant productivity in peatlands (but may also increase peat decomposition rates and reduce permafrost protection of peat).
	TempSeason: Annual Temperature Seasonality (Coefficient of Variation; period 1950-2000)	+/- High TempSeason reflects warm productive summers and cold winters, but it is also correlated to continentality
Precipitation	MAP: Mean Annual Precipitation sum (period 1950-2000)	+ High MAP favours waterlogging (which inhibits aerobic decay and increases peat formation)
	PrecipSeason: Annual Precipitation Seasonality (Coefficient of Variation; period 1950-2000)	+/- May reflect both wet and dry conditions during the growing season
	PET: Annual sum of potential evapotranspiration MAP/PET: The ratio of mean annual precipitation to annual sum of potential evapotranspiration	- High PET limits waterlogging + High MAP/PET indicates precipitation excess which favours waterlogging
Mineral soil texture	Texture: Combined percentage of silt and clay (cohesion soils) mapped in the HWSD	+ Fine textured cohesion soils reduces soil drainage favouring waterlogging
Topography	Topography: A topographic landform classification where rugged terrain has lower values than flat terrain or plains,	+ Low-lying and flat landforms are more prone to peat formation
Peatland extent	Extent: Combined percentage coverage of organic soils	+ Internal controls of peatland hydrology and plant communities promotes continued peat formation

175 2.2 Upscaling peat core data to areal peat depth coverage

176 Upscaling peat properties from point observations to areal coverage can be done using various
 177 methods. Earlier studies have often applied simple thematic mean upscaling (e.g. mean values
 178 used for different classes or spatial units)(Gustaf Hugelius, 2012), but in recent decades digital
 179 soil mapping methods were increasingly used (Minasny et al., 2019). Here we have compared
 180 three different methods: thematic upscaling, Geographically Weighted Regression (GWR) and
 181 Random Forest Machine Learning (RFML). The different analyses and methods are described in

182 more detail in the subsections below. In all statistical modeling the target variable (dependent
183 variable) is vertical peat depth (cm) from the soil surface, which in GWR and RFML is predicted
184 using a set of environmental variables (independent variables) represented by values from
185 spatial maps (Table 1, Table S1). Because of the very high variability in peat depth, and
186 sometimes imprecise geolocations of point data, all maps were resampled to the relatively
187 coarse resolution of 5 km pixels (using an equal area projection).

188 *2.2.1 Geographically Weighted Regression*

189 Informed by the exploratory multiple regression analyses, we proceeded with selection of
190 environmental variables for GWR (Brunsdon et al., 1996; Fotheringham et al., 2002). Based on
191 the result matrix of the multiple regression analyses we selected those environmental variables
192 which (1) statistically significant explanatory variables in the GWR, (2) exhibited consistent
193 explanatory patterns across multiple levels of data aggregation (e.g. a consistent positive or
194 negative relationships to peat depth) and (3) showed limited internal multicollinearity. Based
195 on these criteria the following suitable environmental variables were identified (in ranked
196 order) PET, MTWQ and PrecipSeas. GWR was run with the full range of dependent input data
197 (from all individual points up to a minimum point density of 30 sites per circular neighborhood)
198 and for the spatially smoothed data points as well. For each input dataset, multiple GWRs were
199 run with adaptive bandwidths of $n= 100, 200, 400, 600, 800$ and 1000 sites (resulting in 96
200 different GWR runs). The bandwidth number represents the individual number of target
201 variable data points that are used to locally solve the best regression model. A larger bandwidth
202 will thus use a larger number of points. Because of difficulties with extremely varying data
203 densities and data variabilities across the study domains, most GWR runs were unstable in
204 some regions. We present results from the best (highest adjusted R^2) GWR model which was
205 fully stable and free of collinearity. This model had an adjusted R^2 of 0.38 and a bandwidth of
206 200 sites (i.e., the n sites used to fit the regression at each point). This GWR model was run with
207 spatially aggregated data with ≥ 10 replicate peat depth measurements per 30 km radius circle.
208 It was based on the environmental variables, potential evapotranspiration, mean summer
209 temperature and precipitation seasonality, with a 90×90 km smoothing kernel applied to the
210 gridded data (original resolution 5 km).

211 *2.2.2 Thematic upscaling of peat depths*

212 The thematic upscaling is based on a combination of soil map polygons in the national soil maps
213 and biomes (Olson et al., 2001). Because thematic scaling is best applied within distinct spatial
214 regions (Hugelius, 2012), we used these polygon-based maps rather than the pixel-based
215 SoilGrid maps for these analyses. For those polygons where there was no organic soil coverage
216 mapped, but point data indicated a presence of peatlands, we assumed a 1% peatland cover in
217 that polygon. The upscaling is based on an approach whereby the upscaling unit should have
218 sufficient data points to assess the central tendency and variability in that scaling unit
219 (Hugelius, 2012). This threshold was set relatively low to $n \geq 10$. In those cases where there was
220 sufficient data on peat depth within a single soil map polygon, the mean and standard deviation
221 of those sites were used to calculate mean peat depth and a 95% confidence interval (CI95%).
222 For those soil map polygons where data density was insufficient for this approach, we
223 calculated the $\text{mean} \pm \text{SD}$ peat depth for that individual ecoregion polygon. With this approach

224 there is a risk that the data is less representative of that upscaling unit. To account for that the
225 CI95% was adapted to include a representation error of $\pm 20\%$ of the mean (based on (Gustaf
226 Hugelius et al., 2014)). In the cases where the ecoregion had too little data we merged data for
227 several ecoregions of the same class until the threshold of $n \geq 10$ was reached (with the CI95%
228 adapted to include a representation error of 30%). In the few cases where there was
229 insufficient data in that ecoregion class we merged all data at the biome level (with the CI95%
230 adapted to include a representation error of 40%).

231 2.2.3 Machine Learning upscaling of peat depth

232 A Random Forests model (RFML) was trained using the observational peat depth data. This
233 model is identical to the model used for peat depth mapping in Hugelius et al. (2020). RFML
234 was chosen as a machine learning method based on its robustness towards non-linear
235 relationships between predicted and environmental variables, and its strong general
236 performance in different kind of landscapes (Lamichhane et al., 2019) including for SOC and
237 peatland depth (Siewert, 2018). RFML is a tree based machine-learning method that can use an
238 ensemble of trees for regression estimates (Breiman, 2001). Each regression tree depends on a
239 random selection of environmental predictors that are then averaged, which achieves better
240 results by merging a large number of trees ($n = 1000$ trees). In total 6038 data points with peat
241 depth observations were used for the spatial modeling of peat depth (points in too close
242 proximity or where environmental data was lacking were excluded). Training data was
243 extracted from all spatial environmental predictor variables (table 1) based on locations of
244 target variable data points. One model was done for all variables and a separate model was
245 done using only climate variables. To achieve stable model results, we used a 10- fold cross
246 validation with 5 repetitions for model training using the *caret* package in R (Kuhn, 2008). *Caret*
247 in turn calls the *RandomForest* package (Liaw & Wiener, 2002). To compensate for the
248 regression to mean effect, common for random forest modeling of environmental variables
249 that leads to overestimation of low values and underestimation of high values, we applied bias
250 correction using best angle residual rotation (Song, 2015). The supplemental figures S5 to S7
251 provide information on the internal validation and properties of the final RFML models.

252 2.3 Calculating peat depth, volume and stocks of OC and TN

253 Potential peat OC and TN stocks per map pixel are calculated using linear models to predict
254 OC/TN as a function of peat depth developed by Hugelius et al (2020). This was done on log-
255 transformed data using Major Axis (MA) linear models (Warton et al., 2006) with intercepts set
256 to zero, done separately for permafrost-free and permafrost peatlands, respectively. These
257 models were used to estimate OC ($n = 334$ and 446 ; slopes of 0.850 ± 0.004 and 0.883 ± 0.003 ; R^2 s
258 of 0.77 and 0.57 ; both $p < 0.0001$) and TN ($n = 16$ and 85 ; slopes 0.182 ± 0.02 and 0.312 ± 0.007 ; R^2 s
259 0.35 and 0.42 ; $p < 0.05$ and $p < 0.0001$) from peat depth. We refer to Hugelius et al. (2020) for
260 more details.

261 Spatial maps of peat volume, OC and TN stocks are calculated by multiplying maps of potential
262 peat OC and TN stocks with maps of peatland extent. The peat extent maps analyzed in this
263 paper are similar to those used in Hugelius et al., (2020). In that study, peatland spatial extent is
264 estimated from polygon-based GIS data derived from harmonized regional/national soil
265 classification maps (Hugelius et al., 2013; Hugelius et al., 2020) as well as soil classification data

266 extracted from the global gridded SoilGrids 250 m dataset, produced using machine learning
267 algorithms with soil observational data and a large amount of environmental covariates (Hengl
268 et al., 2017). We refer to Hugelius et al. (2020) for more information on the peatland extent
269 maps and ground-truthing of these maps.
270 Each upscaling method is associated with its own uncertainty metric (see above). To enable
271 comparison between methods we performed a consistent uncertainty estimate for all methods.
272 This was done with the full point datasets for depth, OC stock and TN stock. For each variable
273 we calculated the root mean square error (RMSE) between observed and modelled values for
274 all observations. We also calculated trimmed RMSE (based on 5th/95th percentiles of
275 residuals), R^2 between modelled and observed values and deviation of the mean in modelled
276 and observed. To establish which scaling method was most robust the performance of each
277 method was ranked for these different metrics (using both a normalized weighted ranking and
278 an ordinal ranking). Given the very high variability in the point data (also over short distances),
279 the trimmed RMSE is considered as the most robust estimate of error and this is reported in the
280 main text and used to calculate uncertainty ranges for upscaled peat volume, OC mass and TN
281 mass. For C:N based scaling of total TN mass, the uncertainty range was calculated by
282 combining the error of the OC scaling with the coefficient of variation (COV) of the C:N in a
283 formula for additive error propagation.
284 The accuracy of the broad-scale maps of peat depth have been assessed against data from 15
285 local studies distributed across the studied region (see Table S4 in Hugelius et al. 2020 for
286 detailed descriptions of these areas). Hugelius et al (2020) used these sites to assess peat
287 extent. For this study, the mean peat depth in each of these 15 areas was calculated and
288 compared to that mapped in the broad-scale maps.

289 3 Results

290 3.1 Peat depth and stocks of OC and TN from individual peat cores

291 The mean peat depth across all peat cores is 235 ± 175 cm (range from 40 to 2,000 cm; $n=7,111$).
292 The peat depth in sites where only peat depth data is recorded (241 ± 180 cm) are significantly
293 deeper (Welch F-test, $F=5.4$, $df=264$, $p<0.01$) than the peat cores where there is detailed OC%
294 (mean 206 ± 125 cm; range 40-1,099 cm; $n=782$) and N% data (mean 198 ± 94 cm; range 41-530
295 cm; $n=105$) (Fig. 1a; Fig. S1). Histograms of the overall peat depth-distribution patterns (Fig. S2)
296 show approximately log-normal depth distributions of peat depth.
297 Analyzing the incremental depth distribution of peat volume calculated across all peat cores
298 shows a clear tendency of deeper peatlands in milder climates ($MAAT > 0^\circ \text{C}$), assumed to be
299 permafrost free, than in colder permafrost-affected regions ($MAAT < -1^\circ \text{C}$). In milder and colder
300 climates, respectively, 40% and 25% of the peat volume occurs below 2 m depth (Table 2). The
301 mean depth of peat cores from milder climates is deeper than that of cold climates (255 ± 191
302 cm and 188 ± 132 cm, respectively). There are also significant differences in the climate of the
303 different types of peat core data available in the overall dataset. The MAAT of TN stock sites
304 ($11.5 \pm 3.1^\circ \text{C}$) and OC stock sites ($13.1 \pm 3.7^\circ \text{C}$) are significantly colder than peat depth sites
305 ($13.7 \pm 4.4^\circ \text{C}$; range -7.4° to $+27.8^\circ \text{C}$) (ANOVA, $p<0.01$), suggesting that the dataset is biased
306 towards having more complete OC and TN stock data in northern/colder regions.

307

308 Table 2. Table shows the distribution of peat volume per 1 m depth interval estimated from peat depth
 309 cores. The data is separated into peatlands located in sites with MAAT >0° C (No permafrost) and MAAT
 310 <-1° C (permafrost). This is assumed to correspond to sites without and with permafrost, respectively,
 311 but for many of the sites we lack data on whether permafrost is actually present.

Fraction of total peat volume per depth

Depth	MAAT >0° C (no permafrost) (n=4,876)	MAAT <-1° C (permafrost) (n=2,287)
0-1 m	37%	48%
1-2 m	25%	29%
2-3 m	16%	14%
3-4 m	10%	6%
4-5 m	3%	1%
>5 m	10%	4%

312
 313 The spatial distribution of peat cores is uneven, particularly for sites with OC and TN density
 314 data, which are clustered in peat-rich, northern regions (Fig. 1b). There are systematic
 315 differences, with more detailed data available from the northern permafrost affected
 316 peatlands, which tend to be shallower. More than half of the OC density sites are affected by
 317 permafrost (Fig. 1d). Subdividing the sites with data on OC density by peatland type reveals that
 318 the deepest peat deposits have accumulated in bogs and fens (mean depths 267±171 cm and
 319 248±141 cm, respectively), with permafrost peatlands and post-thaw permafrost peatlands
 320 (mean depths 196±100 cm and 194±110 cm, respectively) having significantly shallower peat
 321 (Fig. 1b; ANOVA, $p < 0.05$; Fig. S3). However, there is no statistically significant difference in
 322 mean peat OC density between these different peatland types (mean OC density 107–125 kg C
 323 m⁻²; ANOVA, $p > 0.05$) except for sites with unknown peatland morphology that have shallower
 324 peat and less peat OC (ANOVA, $p < 0.05$; Fig. S3). The bulk peat C:N was calculated for full peat
 325 cores as the ratio of the OC mass to TN mass per peat core. All peat cores combined have a C:N
 326 of 29±13. The C:N in non-permafrost bogs (40±13) are significantly higher than those of
 327 permafrost (27±13) and post-thaw peatlands (24±13) (ANOVA, $p < 0.05$). There is insufficient
 328 data to evaluate and report C:N from non-permafrost fen peatlands.
 329 While there are clear latitudinal patterns in the overall peat depth, the sub-set of sites for
 330 which OC data is available has less clear spatial patterns. There is substantial spatial variability
 331 in the geographical distribution of measured peat column OC stocks (Fig. 1c). In regions with
 332 high data-density, there is also substantial variability in both peat depth and peat OC stocks.
 333 Semivariogram analyses also show the data properties as spatially variable with a very large
 334 unexplained variance over short distances (nugget effect) and a saturation of spatial
 335 autocorrelation (range) at 250 km (Fig. S3). There is significant spatial clustering and
 336 autocorrelation of peat depth (Global Moran's I index: 0.476, z-score: 28.6; $p < 0.01$). Local
 337 analyses of spatial clustering and outliers reveal relatively consistent patterns of clustering with
 338 deep or shallow peatlands (figure S4). High peat depth outliers are spread evenly across the
 339 domain while low peat depth outliers are more clustered (e.g. in Northern Europe).

340
 341 Figure 1. Panel a shows the percentile distribution of peat depths subdivided for sites with peat depth
 342 data ($n=7111$, all sites), sites with peat OC stock data ($n=782$) and sites with peat TN stock data ($n=105$).
 343 Panel b shows the spatial distribution of peat sites with data on peat depth and peat OC stocks over a
 344 map of biome distributions (adapted from Olsen et al., 2001). Panel c is a cartogram of peat OC sites
 345 where the size of site symbols is proportional to measured peat OC density (kg C m^{-2}) in each site over a
 346 map of peatland extent from the SoilGrids dataset (Hengl et al., 2017). Panel d shows sites with peat OC
 347 density data ($n=782$) subdivided into different peatland types over a map of permafrost zonation (Brown
 348 et al., 1997).

349 3.2 Environmental controls of peat depth and peat density

350 Analyses across all peat depth sites shows that when analyzed individually, none of the
 351 environmental variables is correlated to peat depth (all univariate linear models had R^2 of -0.05
 352 to 0.05, $n=7,011$). This means that none of hypothesized environmental controls on peatland
 353 depth (table 1) is significant on its own. This lack of correlation to patterns of temperature or
 354 precipitation, incoming radiation, topography, soil texture or peatland extent shows that more
 355 complex relationships control vertical peat accumulation. Following on the analyses of
 356 individual variables, multiple regression analyses at different levels of spatial aggregation reveal
 357 some more robust trends (Fig. 2a, table S2).

358 When including only regions with higher data density, the strength of the relationship between
 359 peat depth and the environmental predictors increased. Analyses across regions of successively
 360 higher density of observational peat depth data increases the explanatory power of multiple
 361 regression models from $R^2=0.05$ (for all points) to $R^2=0.45$ for regions with higher data density
 362 ($n>30$ per 30 km radius). For all levels of spatial point aggregation, the best performing multiple
 363 regression models have three or four environmental variables (Table S2). Potential
 364 evapotranspiration (negative regression) in combination with summer air temperature (positive
 365 regression), seasonality of precipitation (negative regression) and seasonality of temperature
 366 (negative regression) are the most robust explanatory variables (Fig. 3b). Solar radiation and
 367 the physiographic variables (topography, soil texture and peatland extent) have limited
 368 influence on peat depth. Applying smoothing filters to the independent environmental grids (to
 369 90*90 km instead of 5*5 km) yields only a limited increase in model skill (Table S2).

370
 371 Figure 2. Panel a shows the R^2 of the best performing multiple regression model (determined through
 372 AIC) for different spatial density levels of available field data. In each incremental step, areas where the
 373 data density is below the given threshold within a 30 km radius were excluded so that fewer, but more
 374 data-dense, peatland areas are retained in the regression model. Panel b shows the number of times
 375 that different environmental variables were included in the best performing models. Signs of + and -
 376 show positive or negative regressions respectively. (Seas. abbreviates seasonality)

377 3.3 Comparing different methods for spatial scaling of peat depth and OC/TN density

378 The maps in figure 3 show predicted potential mean peat depth, should a peatland have
379 formed in any given location. The different methods of scaling the peat core data to potential
380 peat depth yields very different results. The RFML approach gives similar results when using all
381 environmental variables or only the climatic variables (Figs. 3a and 3b, respectively). This
382 suggest that at this coarse spatial scale, physiographic environmental variables add little model
383 skill beyond what can be achieved based on climate alone. This is in line with our findings from
384 multiple regression models, which show that all the most robust environmental predictors are
385 climate variables (Fig. 2). When compared to the RFML maps, the thematic scaling produces
386 similar, but less pronounced, peat depth patterns across regions (Fig. 3c). The spatial patterns
387 in the GWR maps are similar to RFML and thematic scaling in data-dense areas, but differ
388 significantly in areas with low data density (Fig. 3d). Note the very high peat depth predicted by
389 GWR in the southern part of Eurasia, which are opposite to patterns shown by the other
390 techniques. There are very few peatlands in this region, and almost no field data to support the
391 result.

392 The accuracy of the different upscaling methods was assessed against the point observations
393 and a summarized weighed ranking was used to assess the different methods for spatial scaling
394 (Fig. 4a; see table S3 for both normalized and ordinal ranking of all variables). For all three
395 variables, the RFML methods worked best, followed by thematic scaling and last the GWR. The
396 RFML model based on all environmental variables worked marginally better than the RFML
397 model based on climatic variables alone, but the differences are small (Fig. 3ab, Table S3). Only
398 the results of the model based on all variables are shown in figure 4. Comparing the broad scale
399 maps to data from local study areas show that the broad scale maps consistently underestimate
400 peat depth in areas of deep peat and overestimate peat depth in areas of shallow peat (Figure
401 4b).

402 3.4 Comparing peat depth models and peat extent maps for OC/TN stock estimates

403 Combining peatland extent maps (from Hugelius et al., 2020) with the maps of potential peat
404 depth yields maps of scaled peatland OC and TN mean density (kg m^{-2}) from this study can be
405 used to calculate total OC and TN stocks (Table 3). Compared to thematic scaling, the RFML
406 scaling shows deeper peatlands, with more OC and TN (Table 3). The difference between
407 methods for scaling of mean peat depth (11% difference between methods) and total OC stocks
408 (6% difference) is much bigger than the difference between the two separate peat extent maps
409 (3% and <1% difference, respectively). Maps derived from RFML scaling and SoilGrids peatland
410 extent (Figs. 5a, c, d) compared to maps derived from thematic scaling with polygon maps (Figs.
411 5b, d, f) show similar broad-scale patterns but notable local and regional differences. In the
412 thematic scaling with polygon maps, the peat stocks are concentrated to some core regions
413 (e.g. West Siberian and Hudson Bay lowlands), while the RFML/SoilGrids maps shows more
414 distributed peat OC/TN stocks. Although there are small differences in total peat OC stocks
415 between maps, there are very large discrepancies in the mapped extent of permafrost in
416 peatlands. The extent of Histels is almost twice as high in SoilGrids as in the polygon maps.

417
418 Figure 3. Maps of potential mean peatland depths based on the different scaling methods applied. (a)
419 Random Forest Machine using all environmental variables presented in Table 1; (b) Random Forest
420 Machine using only the climatic environmental variables presented in Table 1; (c) thematic scaling based
421 on polygon soil maps and ecoregions; and (d) geographically weighed regression (GWR).

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426 Figure 4. Results summarizing the evaluation of different scaling methods against (a) individual peat
 427 cores and (b) against local maps. Panel (a) shows summed ranking of the different upscaling methods
 428 for mapping peat depth, peat OC density and peat TN density. Only RFML for all variables is shown, but
 429 results for RFML with climate variables is very similar. The ranking is normalized to a scale from 0-1. For
 430 each variable (depth, OC and TN) the most accurate method that is most accurate for R^2 , RMSE and
 431 deviation of the mean, respectively, is scaled to 1 and then the other methods are scored for how much
 432 more they deviate. Note that 1 does not mean a perfect result, it corresponds to the best result
 433 achieved in this study. In fact, all three mapping approaches show large deviations from independent
 434 validation data. Panel (b) shows a comparison of the upscaled peat depth with different methods
 435 mapped compared to the mapped peat depth from local high-resolution and high-quality field studies
 436 (see table S4). The figure includes linear fit to the points for each method for comparison to the 1:1 line.
 437

438 Table 3. Summary of upscaled, area-weighted, peat depth (cm), peat OC storage (kg C m^{-2}) and total stock (Pg C) as
 439 well as peat TN storage (kg N m^{-2}) and total stock (Pg N) based on different maps and methods for estimating peat
 440 depth. For the scaling based on regional maps, the extent from SoilGrids are applied where the regional soil maps
 441 do not cover (5% of the total peatland extent). This correction has been applied to enable direct comparison
 442 between the presented numbers.
 443

	Machine Learning, regional maps				Machine Learning, SoilGrids				Thematic scaling, regional maps			
	Histosol	Histel	Total	RMSE	Histosol	Histel	Total	RMSE	Histosol	Histel	Total	RMSE
Mean peat depth (cm)	282	193	253	97	289	218	245	97	237	197	224	111
Peat OC storage (kg C m^{-2})	116	103	111	41	130	113	119	41	104	106	105	43
Peat OC stock (Pg C)	288	126	414	151	171	245	416	142	260	129	389	161
Peat TN storage (kg N m^{-2})	1.9	4.1	2.7	2.0	1.9	4.3	3.4	2.0	3.0	5.2	3.8	2.0
Peat TN stock (Pg N)	4.3	5.0	9.2	6.8	2.5	9.3	11.8	7.2	6.7	6.3	13.0	6.9

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448 Figure 5. Maps of upscaled peat OC density in all peatlands combined (a, b), Histosols (c, d) and Histels

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450 (e, f). Peat OC stock maps based on peat depth from RFML mapping with peatland extent from SoilGrids

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452 4 Discussion

453 4.1 Environmental controls on peatland depth at different scales

454 Peat depth in northern peatlands is challenging to predict because of the high spatial variability
455 occurring at multiple scales. Peat volume in a landscape is a function of both lateral and vertical
456 extent, but the factors that control peatland initiation and lateral expansion may be different
457 from the controls on peatland depth. Our analyses show no simple linear relationships between
458 any tested environmental variable and peat depth. Although peat deposits occurring in cold
459 climates and affected by permafrost are generally shallower than other northern peatlands,
460 interactions of multiple environmental variables were needed to predict peat depth. The
461 strongest environmental controls on northern peat depth were potential evapotranspiration
462 (PET, negative relationship) and summer temperature (MTWQ, positive regressions), with a
463 weaker influence of precipitation and temperature seasonality (negative regressions; Figure 4).
464 Vertical peat growth is thus favored in regions with lower potential evapotranspiration, but
465 with warm summers and a limited seasonality. Other climatic variables, as well as PAR, were
466 less important in these analyses. This may be caused by high internal correlation between the
467 included climate variables (e.g. PAR and MAAT is correlated to MTWQ). Physiographic and
468 edaphic factors, such as topographic roughness, mineral soil texture or peatland extent were
469 tested but never included as predictors in the best performing multiple regression analyses (Fig.
470 2b). But at the same time, the physiographic variables were important explanatory variables for
471 the machine learning model in spatial predictions of soil depth (Fig. S6).

472 This apparent lack of clear predictive models for peat depth at the hemispheric scale is in
473 contrast to some studies at landscape or peatland basin scale. At landscape scale, topography is
474 an important control of peat depth (Li et al., 2024). At the scale of an individual peatland basin,
475 a recent study showed that the depth of raised bog peat can be accurately predicted from
476 peatland basin shape and surface elevation profiles (Cobb et al., 2024). Such predictions of peat
477 bog growth are based on theoretical understanding and empirical data on how bog peat growth
478 in ombrotrophic systems is determined by internal hydrological feedbacks (Clymo et al., 1998;
479 Gorham et al., 2012). However, there is limited applicability of such models to minerotrophic
480 peat growth; fen deposit morphology is often determined by the pre-existing mineral soil or
481 bedrock basins in which they form (Cobb et al., 2024; Temmink et al., 2022). In many peatland
482 basins, variable underlying topography can cause substantial local-scale variability of peat
483 depth with limited surface expression on the peatland surface (Fyfe et al., 2014; Loisel et al.,
484 2017; Muir et al., 2024; Pluchon et al., 2014). Despite variability in sub-peat basin shapes, local
485 data supports a link between distance to the peatland edge and peat depth (Li et al., 2024; Julie
486 Loisel et al., 2017). Temmink et al. (2022) present generalized conceptual models of feedbacks
487 between peatland vegetation communities, hydrology, and peatland morphology
488 (biogeomorphic feedbacks). They subdivide them into “productivity-stimulating” feedbacks in
489 fen peatlands and “decomposition-limiting” feedbacks in bog peatlands. The evidence from
490 local surveys as well as the framework of overarching biogeomorphic controls on peat growth
491 supported a hypothesis that peat depth is positively correlated to peatland extent (Table 1), but
492 this was not supported by our analyses. In fact, we show that at broad scales, high peatland
493 extent is most frequent between ~60-70° N, where peat is generally shallower (Figs. 3 and 5).

494 We further find that deeper peat tended to occur in isolated peatlands, often in regions of low
495 observational data density (Fig. S9a). We also find that the residuals between modeled (in
496 maps) and observed peat depths are greater in these data-poor regions (Fig S9b). This is likely
497 because isolated peatlands often occur in local topographic depressions (e.g. kettle holes and
498 dead ice block features) where deep peat can accumulate (Campbell et al., 1997; Karasiewicz,
499 2019). This finding is in line with local scale studies emphasizing the importance of sub-peat
500 basin morphology.

501 The myriad of processes that lead to peatland formation, expansion, and peat accumulation
502 lead to complex spatial patterns in peat depth distribution. Some of this complexity may be due
503 to landscape history, which has not been accounted for in this study. For some bog peatlands, it
504 has been shown that peat depth can be calculated as time since peat initiation and the integral
505 of peat vertical accumulation rate over time (Clymo et al., 1998). In addition to time since peat
506 initiation, past climate conditions affect peat development and depth (Treat et al., 2022; Loisel
507 et al. 2017). For example, many sites show high rates of apparent vertical peat accumulation in
508 the early Holocene (Nichols & Peteet 2019, Loisel et al. 2017). Thus, based on the literature,
509 one would expect that time since peat initiation is correlated to peat depth. This is confirmed
510 by analyses of individual peat cores (Treat et al., 2016) which show a weak linear relationship
511 between peat depth and basal peat age (Fig. 6a, $R^2 = 0.33$). However, broad-scale analyses
512 across the full hemisphere scale, again shows no clear linear relationship. We extracted
513 estimated landscape peatland initiation age (adapted from Loisel et al., 2017) for all peatland
514 core locations ($n = 7,111$) and found no apparent relationship between peat initiation age and
515 current peat depth (Fig. 6b; $R^2 = -0.01$). Given clear local-scale findings from many previous
516 studies, this should not be seen as evidence that long-term landscape history does not affect
517 peat depth. Rather, it is an indication that the processes controlling these relationships across
518 broad scale are complex, and non-linear. It is likely that more in-depth analyses could reveal
519 clearer links between peat depth and landscape history.

520
 521 Figure 6. Panel a shows basal peat depth and peat basal age ($n=111$) in individual peat cores from Treat
 522 et al (2016). Panel b shows observed peat depth ($n=7,111$) against estimated first landscape-scale peat
 523 initiation age extracted from an interpolated hemispheric map based on the MGK13S dataset (data
 524 adapted from Loisel et al., 2017). In both panels, histograms (bottom and right) shows the relative
 525 frequency of sites along the x and y axes and red lines show linear regression models with intercept set
 526 to zero (R^2 of 0.33 and -0.01, respectively).
 527

528 It is possible that the large variability and lack of clear patterns in our analyses may partly be an
 529 artefact of sampling. This dataset was compiled from a range of sources, with no possibility of
 530 implementing an overarching sampling strategy tailored for peat depth mapping. Many
 531 individual sites were sampled for other purposes, such as paleo-environmental reconstructions.
 532 Estimating peatland depth from one centrally located peat core may cause systematic
 533 overestimation of peatland depth (Van Bellen et al., 2011). In our large dataset, isolated data
 534 points tend to have very deep peat depths, possibly overestimating regional peat depths,
 535 particularly in data-sparse regions. For future studies, we propose that analyses of properties
 536 representing individual peatland complexes would yield further insights. It is crucial to study
 537 and understand the processes that constrain vertical peat accumulation in fens and bogs, such
 538 as biogeomorphic feedbacks, sub-peat basin morphology and peatland elevation (Cobb et al.,
 539 2024; Ehnvall et al., 2024; Temmink et al., 2022). Rather than using peat cores in combination
 540 with gridded peatland data, future studies should aim towards analyzing properties of multiple
 541 individual peatland complexes.

542 4.2 Comparison of different peat-depth upscaling methods

543 We test three different families of upscaling, including spatially calculated averages in thematic
544 scaling, via geo-spatial regression models to machine learning models. Combining different
545 metrics of method performance shows that RFML performs best, followed by thematic
546 upscaling and with GWR last. The performance of different upscaling methods for any particular
547 task largely depends on the properties of the input data. The dataset of compiled peat depth
548 observations analyzed in this paper is highly spatially clustered with large variability over short
549 distances. Strong spatial variability in peat depths can occur at multiple scales: among adjacent
550 micro-topographical forms within the same wetland (Graham et al., 2020), from differing
551 morphology within distinct peatland basins (Comas et al., 2011; Goyette et al., 2024), or large
552 differences between spatially adjacent peatlands (Robitaille et al., 2021). The high spatial
553 variability of peatland data have caused difficulties for previous studies using techniques that
554 rely on spatial autocorrelation (e.g. Brogniez et al., 2015). Thematic scaling often produces
555 estimates with robust central tendencies, provided that replication is sufficient (Hugelius,
556 2012), but the spatial maps produced in this study provide limited detail or range of
557 predications. GWR can work well on spatially clustered data, but it can be sensitive to limited
558 spatial autocorrelation in the data (Fotheringham et al., 2002) and it did not perform well in this
559 study. Especially in areas of low data density, and with very high data variability over short
560 distances, GWR predictions deviate significantly from the other methods (see southern regions
561 in figure 5). Given the spatially clustered and noisy data, poor performance by the GWR method
562 can be expected. But machine learning (ML) methods have been shown to produce relatively
563 robust results also with difficult data. RFML has been frequently used in digital soil mapping
564 (Forkuor et al., 2017) as well as for depth estimates in Arctic and tropical peatland
565 environments (Crezee et al., 2022; Rudiyanto et al., 2016; Siewert, 2018). The ability of ML
566 methods to cope with clustered and noisy data manifested by the best performance also in this
567 study. RFML is particularly well suited for peatlands and soil carbon density as it is less sensitive
568 to non-linear patterns in the landscape (Siewert 2018). However, comparison to local-scale
569 studies shows that our broad-scale maps are not able to recreate the true range and variability
570 of peat depth (Figure 4b). However, the average peat depth over larger regions is likely
571 consistent with the calculated uncertainty ranges. This comparison highlights that broad scale
572 maps should not be used in local analyses.

573 4.3 Impact of mapping methods on peat OC or stock estimates

574 Early estimates of northern peat OC or TN stocks have been obtained using three approaches:
575 (1) from generalized national inventories of peat extent, peat depth and peat properties
576 (Gorham, 1991) (2) by estimating carbon density as a function of peat depth from many
577 individual peat cores (MacDonald et al., 2006) and (3) by estimating peat carbon accumulation
578 over time based on well-constrained chronologies from individual peat cores (Yu, 2012). In
579 more recent studies, combining peat profile data and environmental covariates with machine
580 learning modeling is more common (Minasny et al., 2023). But many peatland maps created
581 using other methods are still frequently used. Recent and emerging global wetland and
582 peatland extent maps combine a multitude of data sources, created using several different
583 methods (Lehner et al., 2024; Olefeldt et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2021). Another recent study
584 used machine learning algorithms trained from existing peatland extent maps (with varying

585 origin, age and methodology) to make a global peat extent map (Melton et al., 2022). Thus,
586 broad scale peat maps created using many different methods are still widely used, but it has
587 not been systematically evaluated how mapping methods affect map accuracy, or how
588 significant the differences in peat C stocks are resulting from these maps.
589 Peat OC stock is often estimated by combining separate maps of peat depth and of peatland
590 areal extent (Hugelius et al., 2020). Using the updated peat depth maps generated in this study,
591 we estimate northern peat OC stocks of 390–420 Pg, which is in line with most previous
592 estimates of northern peatland OC stocks (Z. Yu et al., 2021). In our comparison of different
593 maps and methods (Table 3), we find larger differences between peat depth upscaling methods
594 (25 Pg OC difference) than between peat extent maps (2 Pg OC difference). This is due to a
595 remarkable consistency in total mapped peatland extent between SoilGrids and the regional
596 polygon maps. But while the total area is similar, there are substantial differences in both
597 spatial patterns of peat distribution and in the area of mapped Histels (figure 6). The Histels in
598 SoilGrids are largely mapped in known permafrost regions; 90% of the Histels in SoilGrids are
599 mapped within the permafrost extent of (Brown et al., 2002) and 97% within the permafrost
600 extent of (Gruber, 2012). Since permafrost in peatlands is less sensitive to thaw than mineral
601 soil permafrost (due to the insulating properties of peat) isolated permafrost peatlands may
602 occur in areas with MAAT well over 0° C (Hugelius et al., 2020). However, in some areas the
603 mapped distribution of Histels in SoilGrids is unrealistic. One such example is Histels mapped in
604 lowlands of the central Scandinavian peninsula (figure 5e) where MAAT has been >2–3° C for a
605 century and more (Harris et al., 2020) and we find no occurrences of Histels reported in
606 scientific literature or national inventories. It is thus likely that SoilGrids overestimates the
607 extent of Histels.

608 4.4 Deep peat deposits adds to global soil OC stock estimates

609 Estimates of global peat OC stocks are independent from global estimates of total soil OC
610 stocks, which include some, but not all peatland OC stocks. To date, the degree to which
611 different estimates overlap has not been fully reconciled. Much of the peat volume mapped in
612 our study occurs below the depths included in global maps of estimated soil carbon stocks.
613 (Jackson et al., 2017) combine different datasets to estimate a total global soil C stock of 2,800
614 Pg C down to 3 m depth. They also describe an estimated ~30–50 Pg OC in tropical peatlands
615 below 3 m depth but had no data to quantify peat OC stocks below 3 m depth in northern
616 peatlands. Our peat depth data suggest that, south of the permafrost region, 23% of total peat
617 volume occurs below 3 m depth (Table 2). In the permafrost region, 11% of peat OC lies below
618 3 m depth. Assuming that the depth distribution of peat volume (from Table 2) is proportional
619 to the depth distribution of peat OC stocks (Table 3), we estimate that northern peatlands store
620 ca. 50–100 Pg peat OC below 3 m depth (40–70 Pg in Histosols and 10–30 Pg in Histels). This peat
621 OC stock which was not included in global soil OC stock estimates by Jackson et al. (2017) or by
622 the IPCC 6th assessment report WGI (Canadell et al., 2021). There is some concern that the
623 assumptions made in these calculations may not be robust to systematic differences in peat C
624 density with depth. In individual peat cores, compaction tends to cause increased peat density
625 with depth (Z. Yu et al., 2010). But across broad scales and large amounts of data, there is no
626 evidence that peat bulk density, peat OC% content or peat C density systematically increases
627 with depth (Fig. S9)(Julie Loisel et al., 2014), thus these numbers are likely robust.

628 5. Conclusions

629 When analyzed across the extratropical north, peat depth is not correlated to any specific
630 environmental variable. Non-linear models or combinations of multiple explanatory variables
631 are needed to achieve statistically significant models. Even moderate explanatory power
632 (maximum $R^2=0.45$) could only be achieved for areas with relatively high data density. For
633 spatial mapping of peat depths, a random forest machine learning methods works better than a
634 geographically weighted regression based method or thematic upscaling. This is mainly due to
635 the random forest method being robust with the highly clustered and spatially variable peat
636 depth data that is available. The analyses suggest that at broad scales, the controls of peatland
637 lateral extent are different from the controls on peatland depth. We find that higher peat depth
638 is linked to areas with low potential evapotranspiration, warm summers and limited intra-
639 annual climatic seasonality, but these conditions generally do not occur where peatland extent
640 is greatest. This in turns suggest that broad-scale spatial upscaling, or process-based modelling,
641 of peatland dynamics and C stocks should treat lateral peatland expansion and vertical peat
642 growth separately. For example, in a land surface or ecosystem model simulation of peat
643 growth over time, functions for lateral peatland growth should be separate for functions of
644 vertical growth.

645 Despite the large amount of field data analyzed, this study yields relatively limited predictive
646 power for peat depth across broad scales; nor does it provide sufficient process understanding.
647 To enable deeper insights into how and why peatland depth varies in time and space, a new
648 generation of peatland maps as well as improved knowledge on peatland inception dates are
649 needed. The next generation of broad-scale peatland maps should aim to move beyond
650 estimates of fractional peatland coverage within large pixels or polygons. Individual peatland
651 basins should be delineated as distinct objects from high resolution geospatial data. Combining
652 in-situ data collection with mapping of distinct peatland borders and complexes would enable
653 studies of how the genesis and morphology of individual peatland basins are tied to peat depth
654 across space and time. Such data is needed to significantly improve our understanding of how
655 peat depths, and OC/TN stocks, vary in space and time.

656

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665

666 Open Research

667 All geospatial peat depth data generated for this paper is available as GIS files in this folder:
668 <https://stockholmuniversity.box.com/s/hb49y2br22g7fxodrd9ubqyi8ye7ptn4>. If the paper is published they
669 will be uploaded to a separate data repository which assigns DOIs.
670

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